

The Role of Reflexivity in Shaping Educational Research: Separating the Personal from the Professional

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Reflexivity holds significant importance in educational research, particularly for researchers who navigate the complexities of both insider and outsider perspectives in their studies. This paper explores the role of reflexivity in shaping the findings of educational research through the lens of an insider-outsider researcher who is conducting a wider research study on low socioeconomic status (LSES) students in Ireland. By acknowledging and carefully balancing their personal experiences and professional objectivity, researchers can mitigate biases and enhance the accuracy of their findings. Reflexivity involves a researcher's continuous self-examination, considering how their background, beliefs, and interactions with participants influence the research process and outcomes. This paper explores the importance of maintaining a clear separation between personal and professional identities to preserve research integrity, strategies for self-reflection to uncover biases, and methods for ensuring fair and rigorous data interpretation. The researcher's dual perspective provides nuanced insights that contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of educational phenomena. This paper emphasises the significance of reflexivity in action, illuminating how researchers' positionality shapes knowledge production in educational research. By advocating for reflexive practices that enhance the validity of findings and promote transparency and ethical conduct, this paper deepens the understanding of how reflexivity can improve the quality of research and enhance the validity of findings and promote transparency and ethical conduct.

Keywords: Reflexivity; Educational Research; Insider-Outsider; Biases; Positionality

Key Highlights

- **Insider-Outsider Perspective:** Emphasising the role of reflexivity in navigating dual researcher perspectives.
- **Reflexivity Practices:** Detail how methods like reflection diaries and peer debriefing sustain reflexivity, balance personal insights and strengthen research validity.
- **Impact of Positionality on Knowledge Production:** Demonstrates how a researcher's background influences data interpretation, fostering ethical and comprehensive research in education.

Introduction

This paper explores reflexivity through the experiences of a researcher conducting research with LSES students in Ireland. The introduction outlines the significance of reflexivity, the challenges of insider-outsider roles, and provides an overview of the researcher's position. Reflexivity is essential in educational research, especially for those navigating the boundary between insider and outsider roles (Berger, 2015; Holmes, 2020). Reflexivity is often confused with reflection; however, the two are distinct (Finlay, 2002, p. 532). Reflection involves thinking about events after they occur, while Reflexivity is the continuous act of critically analysing one's own prejudices, presumptions, and influences when conducting research (Narayanasamy, 2015). This paper is a personal reflection and exploration of the significance of reflexivity, based on a researcher's experiences while conducting a research study on the 'impact of social and cultural capital on students from low socio-economic status in their progression to further and higher education.' As an insider-outsider researcher, this paper highlights how reflexivity shapes research findings and contributes to the overall integrity and depth of educational research (Mullings, 1999).

Literature Review

Berger (2015) emphasised the importance of reflexivity in qualitative research, highlighting how it helps researchers acknowledge and mitigate biases, thus enhancing the credibility of their findings. Reflexivity in educational research involves continuous self-examination and critical reflection on how researchers' backgrounds, beliefs, and interactions influence their studies (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 235) with recent studies, such as Embury et al., (2020) and Hinostroza-Paredes, (2023) highlighting its necessity in evolving educational landscapes. Positionality, closely related to reflexivity, refers to the recognition of a researcher's social and cultural position and its impact on the research process (Holmes,

2020; Njeri, 2021). This concept is crucial in contexts where researchers have personal connections to their study subjects, as it requires a nuanced approach to balance insider and outsider perspectives (Mullings, 1999; Dhillon and Thomas, 2019). Over the years, numerous studies have investigated the roles of reflexivity and positionality in educational research (Carspecken, 1996; Denzin and Lincoln, 2017). For example, Devine (2011) studied how researchers' personal experiences affect their interpretations and interactions with participants. Similarly, Gair (2012) discussed the challenges and benefits of researchers' dual roles as insiders and outsiders, arguing that this duality can lead to deeper insights but requires careful self-reflection to avoid biases. More recent studies, such as Baxter and Kavanagh (2019), explore the integration of reflexivity within participatory action research, highlighting its impact on both the research process and outcomes. Embury et al., (2020) emphasise the need for continuous reflexive practices to address evolving educational landscapes. However, there is a gap in the literature regarding practical strategies for implementing reflexivity in educational research, particularly in the context of low socioeconomic status (LSES) settings in Ireland. Studies such as Darmody et al., (2014) and Kassan et al., (2020) have highlighted the need for more comprehensive approaches to address the complexities of researcher positionality in an educational context, and this paper seeks to address these gaps by examining the role of reflexivity from the standpoint of an insider-outsider researcher in Irish educational settings, particularly focusing on how personal and professional identities are balanced to maintain research integrity and enhance the accuracy of the findings. Reflexivity in educational research has been widely discussed as a critical component for ensuring the integrity and depth of research. Scholars such as Pillow (2003) and Berger (2015) argue that reflexivity not only helps uncover researchers' biases but also enhances the transparency and ethical conduct of the research process. By examining how researchers' positionality

influences their engagement with participants and the interpretation of data, reflexivity contributes to a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of educational phenomena.

Insider/Outsider

Navigating the dual perspective of being both insider and outsider presents unique challenges and opportunities (Shaw, 2005; Greene, 2014). On one hand, this duality allows the researcher to leverage their deep, personal understanding of the community, culture, and context being studied, providing richer and more nuanced insights that might be inaccessible to a purely external observer (Gair, 2012; Unluer, 2012; Hayfield and Huxley, 2015). However, it also introduces the risk of personal biases and preconceived notions influencing the research process and outcomes, necessitating constant, critical self-reflection to ensure objectivity and credibility (Hayfield and Huxley, 2015; Kassan et al., 2020). Conversely, as an outsider, a researcher may bring a degree of objectivity and draw conclusions an insider may not (Hayfield and Huxley, 2015 p. 92), but might lack the depth of understanding that comes from lived experiences within specific communities, therefore, Berger (2015) suggests a careful balancing of personal experiences with professional objectivity is crucial to mitigate bias and enhance the accuracy of the findings. Furthermore, these dual roles require a sophisticated approach to reflexivity, in which the researcher must continuously negotiate and reconcile their intimate connection to the subject matter with the need for professional detachment and methodological rigor. This dynamic interplay can enrich the research but also demands heightened awareness of how one's positionality shapes the data collection, analysis, and interpretation stages of the research (Holmes, 2020).

Reflexivity

Reflexivity involves a heightened awareness of how a researcher's background, beliefs, and interactions with participants can influence the research process and outcomes. This awareness is particularly important in educational research, where the context and experiences of both researchers and participants significantly shape the data collected and interpretations drawn (Smyth and Banks, 2012; Hayfield and Huxley, 2015). According to O'Reilly and Kiyimba, (2015), reflexivity requires researchers to critically examine their positionality, social and cultural position, and how it affects their research. This paper explores the intricate dynamics of reflexivity in educational research, focusing on the contexts in which researchers have personal connections and lived experiences. Important topics addressed in this paper include the separation of personal and professional identities to maintain research integrity, strategies for self-reflection to uncover and address biases, and methods for ensuring fair and rigorous data interpretation. By examining these topics, this paper provides insights into the complex interplay between a researcher's positionality and the production of knowledge (Corlett and Mavin, 2018). The dual perspective of an insider-outsider researcher offers a nuanced understanding of educational phenomena that might otherwise be overlooked (Brannick and Coghlan, 2007; Hayfield and Huxley, 2015).

Researcher Position

This paper is particularly informed by the researcher's personal and professional experience. Growing up in an area of low socioeconomic status (LSES) and facing economic, social, and cultural issues in everyday life their educational journey was shaped by significant challenges. Despite these obstacles, the researcher returned to education later in life and became an educator and researcher who was deeply aware of the barriers faced by students from similar backgrounds. These experiences have profoundly influenced their research

approach, emphasising the importance of reflexivity in understanding and addressing educational inequities. In contexts where researchers have personal ties to the subject matter, it is crucial to separate personal and professional identities to maintain research integrity (European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, 2023). By distinguishing between their personal perspectives and their role as a researcher, they can critically examine and mitigate biases that may arise from their background. The National Forum on Research Integrity in Ireland reinforces the importance of managing personal biases and keeping objectivity to safeguard research integrity, particularly in social sciences and educational research (Irish Universities Association, 2022). Through structured training, Irish institutions aim to equip researchers with the skills needed to manage personal influences in their work, thus upholding ethical standards in academic research. This practice supports methodological rigor and ensures that findings are rooted in objective analysis rather than personal experience. Reflexivity is not merely an abstract concept, but a practical necessity in educational research and by maintaining critical awareness of their own positionality and its impact on their work, researchers can enhance the validity, transparency, and ethical integrity of their studies (Berger, 2015). This paper provides a reflection of reflexivity in action, drawing on the researcher's dual perspective as an insider-outsider, to offer a comprehensive analysis of the role of reflexivity in shaping educational research findings. The following section, outlines the methods adopted for this study, providing an account of how reflexivity is integrated into the stages of the research process.

Methods

This paper focuses on the reflexive approach within a larger qualitative study examining the impact of social and cultural capital on the educational progression of students from LSES DEIS (Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools) post primary schools.

Reflexivity was critical due to the researcher's dual positionality. Reflexivity was a focus of the researcher's study, ensuring methodological rigor and enhancing the reliability and validity of the findings. Acknowledging the role of social and cultural capital in their own progression from pupil to student to academic researcher, the researcher recognised reflexivity as essential not only for understanding participants' experiences but also for navigating and challenging personal biases that might otherwise influence the overall study's findings. This study employed a reflexive approach that included keeping detailed reflection diaries and conducting regular peer debriefing sessions. These practices were crucial for identifying and mitigating biases, as documented in Table 1 (see below):

Table 1: Reflexive Practices and Their Contributions to Research Rigor

Reflexive practice	Description	Contribution to Research Rigor
Reflection Diaries	Detailed journaling of the researcher's thoughts and biases.	Enhanced self-awareness identified potential biases.
Peer Debriefing	Regular fortnightly meetings with colleagues/peers to discuss research progress.	Provided critical feedback and ensured objective analysis.

The methodological rigor was further underpinned by theoretical frameworks such as Bourdieu's (1990) theory of social and cultural capital. This connection underscores the importance of reflexivity in maintaining the integrity and objectivity of educational research, also the connection between rigorous reflexivity and social and cultural capital not only

reinforces the reliability of the findings but also underscores how reflexivity allows researchers to critically engage with the influence of their backgrounds on the research process, as emphasised by Berger (2015).

The reflection diaries provided a structured approach to capturing real-time insights and biases, while peer debriefings offered critical feedback. These practices ensured that the data interpretation, collection, analysis approaches and methods remained as objective and comprehensive as possible. While the broader study employed qualitative data collection methods, including questionnaires and focus groups, the conceptual framework of reflexivity underpinned all aspects of the research design.

Reflexivity is a critical methodological element because of the researcher's dual positionality as both an insider and an outsider in the study context. This dual role highlights the inherent complexities of conducting educational research within one's community or field. The insider-outsider perspective, as conceptualised by Dwyer and Buckle (2009), involves navigating between familiar and unfamiliar roles, which can both inform and challenge the research process. As an insider, the researcher had access to deep contextual insights but also faced potential biases from personal experiences. Conversely, as an outsider, the researcher brought a fresh perspective that helped question assumptions and reveal new understandings (Bourke, 2014). To manage these complexities, the reflexive framework for this study involved two main practices: the use of a research reflection diary and the implementation of peer debriefing sessions. The research reflection diary is a vital tool for documenting the researcher's evolving thoughts, biases, and emotional responses throughout the data collection and analysis phases. This practice allowed for continuous self-examination and critical reflection on how the researcher's positionality influenced the research process and outcomes. Reflective journaling aligns with contemporary approaches to reflexivity, which emphasise

ongoing self-awareness and the documentation of subjective experiences as they impact research (Finlay, 2008; Gergen et al., 2009).

Fortnightly peer debriefing sessions with colleagues provided an added layer of reflexivity by facilitating discussions that offered external feedback on the research process and the preliminary findings. These sessions were instrumental in identifying potential biases and refining the research approach, thereby enhancing the credibility and rigor of the study. This practice is consistent with the current best practices in qualitative research, which advocates regular external reviews to strengthen the research process (Yin, 2009; Yin, 2015). By emphasising these reflexive practices, the paper contributes to the conceptual framework of reflexivity in educational research and focuses on how these methods facilitate a more nuanced and critical examination of the researcher's role and impact on their overall study's findings, demonstrating how reflexivity serves as both a methodological and conceptual tool for enhancing research validity (Creswell, 2016; Lather, 2016). This approach underscores the importance of reflexivity as a foundational element in research methodologies, distinct from the specific data collection methods used in the larger study and examining the reflexive practices employed, this paper highlights how a conscious and systematic approach to reflexivity can uncover deeper insights and foster more critical engagement with the researcher's positionality (Guba and Lincoln, 2005; Maxwell, 2018).

Ethical Considerations

The ethical implications of reflexivity, particularly concerning the researcher's dual insider/outsider status, were carefully considered. Reflexivity informed every ethical decision, from obtaining participation and informed consent to maintaining confidentiality and ensuring objectivity. Regular reflection and peer debriefing sessions helped mitigate biases and uphold the study's ethical integrity. Participants in the broader study were recruited through

collaboration with DEIS post-primary schools in Dublin, with recruitment involving the researcher delivering face-to-face presentations and talks to potential participants to highlight the study's purpose and invite voluntary participation, thus ensuring an ethically sound and consensual selection process. The participants were selected based on interest and willingness to participate in the study. To ensure a diverse representation of students from low socioeconomic status (LSES) backgrounds, DEIS schools were chosen as they are situated in areas identified as high LSES by Pobal (2022; 2023). Numerous government departments and state agencies for the identification of geographic disadvantages, to target resources and services towards communities most in need use The Pobal HP Deprivation Index as it is Ireland's primary social gradient tool. The percentage of students with high performance (HP) score of -10 or lower, as well as the school's standardised disadvantage score, is used to determine which schools are eligible to participate in the DEIS program. The DEIS program includes schools with the highest levels of disadvantage based on either of these metrics (Department of Education, 2022).

While the broader study addressed standard ethical practices such as informed consent and confidentiality, this paper emphasises the importance of a reflexive approach to maintain ethical rigor and researcher credibility. Obtaining informed consent in the overall study was an extensive process that ensured all participants, and their guardians were fully informed about the research's purpose, their rights, and the voluntary nature of their participation. The researcher visited each participating school, addressing any concerns, and establishing rapport with the students (Bryman, 2016). This direct engagement fostered trust and facilitated open communication, which is crucial for managing the ethical implications of insider/outsider research roles (Mertens, 2021). The Plain Language Statement was designed to ensure full comprehension, describing the study's goals, voluntary nature, and confidentiality protections in accessible terms. During school visits, the researcher distributed

and explained the statement in person, addressing participant and guardian questions. Informed Consent Forms were then signed, with assent obtained from underage participants to confirm their understanding and voluntary participation. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the research process, with all data pseudonymised; identifying information was removed and replaced with codes. Consent and assent agreements were secured, and data was securely stored with access limited to the researcher. Utmost care was taken to ensure that findings will be disseminated in a way that preserve participant anonymity (Wiles, 2012). In addition to standard ethical practices, a reflexive approach was central to addressing the ethical challenges associated with the researcher's positionality as both an insider and outsider. The researcher's personal experiences of educational barriers and background in LSES environments shaped the understanding of the study's context and informed the approach to maintaining objectivity. This self-awareness was crucial for mitigating potential biases and ensuring the credibility of the research process (Luttrell, 2019). Reflecting on positionality required continuous self-evaluation and critical examination of how these experiences might influence the research process and outcomes, which was essential for managing the ethical implications of the dual insider/outsider role and highlighted how reflexivity functions as an ethical tool for maintaining research integrity (Finlay, 2008). Keeping a research reflection diary allowed the researcher to regularly document personal insights, biases, and reactions, which helped maintain a critical perspective throughout the study (Ortlipp, 2008). Peer debriefing sessions with colleagues provided external feedback on these reflections and helped identify potential biases, thereby ensuring the study's ethical rigor (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). While standard ethical considerations, such as informed consent and confidentiality, were addressed, the core of the ethical focus in this paper lies in the application of a reflexive approach to navigate the complexities of insider/outsider positionality. By emphasising reflexivity, this paper illustrates how ethical research practices

extend beyond procedural compliance to include ongoing self-awareness and critical examination of the researcher's role in the study (Maxwell, 2018; Lather, 2016).

Analysis, Results, and Discussion

The primary purpose of this paper is to emphasise the significance of reflexivity in the research process, particularly from an insider-outsider perspective, and to evaluate the impact of engaging with reflexivity principles on the research outcomes. A major insight from this study was the importance of reflexivity in the research process. Engaging in reflexive practices allowed for a deeper understanding of how personal experiences and biases influence research outcomes, making the analysis more authentic and ethically grounded. Practical reflexivity methods, such as maintaining a research reflection diary and participating in peer debriefing sessions, proved effective for maintaining objectivity and continuously addressing potential biases. Recognising and managing conflicts of interest also emerged as essential to conducting research that remains both credible and ethical. These practices underscored the value of reflexivity as a tool not only for self-awareness but for upholding ethical rigor throughout the research journey. The choice to focus on students from LSES stemmed from two pillars: firstly, the researcher's professional pillar, noting that only 10% of Ireland's higher education population comes from disadvantaged areas (HEA, 2020), and that research has shown that social and cultural barriers faced by 'disadvantaged' students are hindering their educational prospects (Lynch & O'Riordan, 1998; McCoy et al., 2010; GUI, 2012; Smyth & Banks, 2012; Torgerson et al., 2014). The complexities of these barriers appear to persist despite various access routes and initiatives. Secondly, from the researcher's personal pillar, as someone with lived experience in a similar context, the researcher recognised the barriers LSES students often face in accessing opportunities, which may be intensified by limited

social and cultural capital. This connection informed a nuanced approach to the analysis, considering both the barriers and strengths inherent in such backgrounds.

For instance, during focus groups (FG) with LSES students, reflexive journaling helped uncover potential biases. In one case, preconceptions about the students' motivations were challenged when a student shared their complex family dynamics. This reflexive insight sparked a deeper examination of family influence in the data analysis, leading to more nuanced findings. By consciously adopting a more open-ended approach in subsequent FGs, it was revealed that many students also struggled with emotional and psychological challenges, such as low self-esteem and lack of parental support. This reflexive adjustment enriched the analysis, resulting in more detailed, responsive, and accurate findings, furthermore the reflection highlights how understanding one's positionality and biases can lead to a more ethical and effective research practice. The practice of reflexivity significantly influenced the research process and outcomes, and by maintaining a research reflection diary and engaging in peer debriefing sessions, it became possible to continuously evaluate and address personal biases and assumptions. This ongoing self-examination was crucial for recognising how the dual role as an insider-outsider researcher could affect various stages of the research, from the formulation of research questions to data collection and analysis. These reflexive practices enabled the identification of potential biases stemming from personal experiences and views, and by acknowledging these biases, necessary steps were taken to mitigate their impact on the research process. By engaging in self-reflection and seeking feedback through peer debriefing sessions, the research design and methods were validated, ensuring that the study's outcomes were both credible and reliable. The dual roles of insider and outsider provided a richer, more nuanced understanding of the research context, demonstrating how reflexivity can transform personal experiences into critical insights for the research process and create balanced perspectives. Reflecting on these aspects helped to manage the researcher's role effectively,

ensuring that the research process was conducted with integrity and rigor. The principles of reflexivity are foundational to producing credible and ethical research, as discussed by Berger (2015) and Holmes (2020). This paper supports the argument that reflexivity is not just a methodological tool but a critical aspect of the researcher's role in shaping knowledge production (Mullings, 1999), with the significance of these findings lying in the demonstration that reflexive practices can lead to more rigorous and ethical research. Reflecting on biases and positionality helped to ensure that the study's outcomes were not inappropriately influenced by personal preconceptions, aligning with Smyth and Banks's (2012) assertion that reflexivity is essential for understanding how a researcher's background impacts the research process and outcomes. In the broader context of educational research, this study underscores the importance of a reflexive approach to ensure that research findings are both accurate and fair. It reinforces the need for researchers to be aware of their own influences on the research process and to adopt practices that promote transparency and ethical conduct (O'Reilly and Kiyimba, 2015).

Conclusions

This paper highlights the pivotal role of reflexivity in educational research through the demonstration of how reflexive practices can enhance research validity and ethical integrity in a qualitative study. Key findings include the importance of ongoing self-reflection and peer feedback in mitigating biases. Future research should continue to integrate reflexive practices to improve the credibility and ethical standards of educational research. The findings align with Bourdieu's theory (1990) of social and cultural capital, which emphasises the role of researchers' backgrounds in shaping their perspectives. Reflexivity, as discussed by Berger (2015), complements this theoretical framework by providing a mechanism to critically examine and mitigate the influence of researchers' social positions. This theoretical grounding

underscores the validity of reflexive practices in producing reliable and unbiased educational research. This paper offers valuable insights for educational researchers and practitioners, highlighting the critical role of reflexivity in enhancing the quality and ethical standards of research and underscores several important implications for practice in the field of educational research. Firstly, it is essential for researchers to integrate reflexivity into their research methodologies to safeguard the integrity of their findings. Engaging in reflexive practices allows researchers to become more aware of their personal biases and their potential impact on the research process, thereby enhancing the credibility and validity of their results (Berger, 2015; Alvesson and Sköldberg, 2017). Additionally, educational institutions have a significant role in emphasising the importance of reflexivity through their research training programs. By incorporating reflexive practices into these programs, institutions can equip future researchers with the skills necessary to balance personal and professional perspectives, which is crucial for conducting rigorous and ethical research (Holmes, 2020; Gair, 2012). In policy contexts, promoting reflexive practices within research funding guidelines and evaluation criteria could encourage researchers across disciplines to adopt these principles, leading to more reliable and ethically sound outcomes. Furthermore, this paper advocates for the development of robust ethical frameworks that explicitly incorporate reflexive practices. Such frameworks are vital for guiding researchers in the management of their positionality and ensuring that research outcomes are both fair and accurate (O'Reilly and Kiyimba, 2015; Mertens, 2023). For researchers operating within similar contexts, especially those with insider-outsider dynamics, these findings provide a methodological approach that reinforces objectivity and transparency, essential for broader applicability and rigor. Reflecting on these practices allows researchers to advance more ethical and effective methodologies, ultimately fostering growth in the field of educational research. These practices not only improve individual research

efforts but also help establish a foundation for future studies that uphold the highest standards of ethical and methodological rigor (Smyth and Banks, 2012; Finlay, 2002).

References

- Alvesson, M. and Sköldböck, K., (2017). Reflexive methodology: New vistas for qualitative research.
- Berger, R. (2015). Now I see it, now I don't: Researcher's position and reflexivity in qualitative research. *Qualitative Research*, 15(2), 219-234.
- Brannick, T. and Coghlan, D., (2007). In defense of being "native": The case for insider academic research. *Organisational research methods*, 10(1), pp.59-74.
- Bourke, B., (2014). Positionality: Reflecting on the research process. *The qualitative report*, 19(33), pp.1-9.
- Bourdieu, P., (1990). The logic of practice. Stanford university press.
- Bryman, A., (2016). Social research methods. Oxford university press.
- Carspecken, F.P., (2013). *Critical ethnography in educational research: A theoretical and practical guide*. Routledge.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K., (2018). Research Methods in Education. 8th ed. London: Routledge.
- Corlett, S. and Mavin, S., (2018). Reflexivity and researcher positionality. *The SAGE handbook of qualitative business and management research methods*, pp.377-399.
- Creswell, J.W. and Poth, C.N., (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage publications.
- Darmody, M., Byrne, D. and McGinnity, F., (2014). Cumulative disadvantage? Educational careers of migrant students in Irish secondary schools. *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 17(1), pp.129-151.
- Denzin, N. K., and Lincoln, Y. S. (2017). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research*. (5 ed.) SAGE Publishing.
- Denzin, N.K., Lincoln, Y.S. and Giardina, M.D., (2006). Disciplining qualitative research. *International journal of qualitative studies in education*, 19(6), pp.769-782.
- Devine, D., (2011). Immigration and schooling in the Republic of Ireland: Making a difference?. Manchester University Press.
- Dhillon, J.K. and Thomas, N., (2019). Ethics of engagement and insider-outsider perspectives: issues and dilemmas in cross-cultural interpretation. *International journal of research and method in education*, 42(4), pp.442-453.
- Dwyer, S.C. and Buckle, J.L., (2009). The space between: On being an insider-outsider in qualitative research. *International journal of qualitative methods*, 8(1), pp.54-63.
- Embury, D.C., Parenti, M. and Childers-McKee, C., (2020). A charge to educational action researchers. *Action Research*, 18(2), pp.127-135.
- European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, ALLEA, (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. Revised edition. Berlin: All European Academies (ALLEA). Available at: <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/> (Accessed: 1 Nov. 2024).

- Finlay, L., (2002). "Outing" the researcher: The provenance, process, and practice of reflexivity. *Qualitative health research*, 12(4), pp.531-545.
- Finlay, L., (2008). Reflecting on 'Reflective practice'.
- Gair, S., (2012). Feeling their stories: Contemplating empathy, insider/outsider positionings, and enriching qualitative research. *Qualitative health research*, 22(1), pp.134-143.
- Gergen, K.J., (2009). Relational being: Beyond self and community. Oxford university press.
- Greene, M.J., (2014). On the inside looking in: Methodological insights and challenges in conducting qualitative insider research. *The qualitative report*, 19(29), pp.1-13.
- Growing Up in Ireland Study Team (2012). Key findings: 13-year olds, School experiences among 13- year-olds. Dublin: ESRI/TCD/DCYA.
- Guba, E.G, and Lincoln, Y.S, (2005). Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences. In N.K Denzin and Y.S Lincoln (Eds). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research* (3rd Ed., pp. 191-215). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Hayfield, N. and Huxley, C., (2015). Insider and outsider perspectives: Reflections on researcher identities in research with lesbian and bisexual women. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 12(2), pp.91-106.
- Higher Education Authority (HEA), (2020). New HEA Data provides in-depth insight into the socio-economic profile of our universities and institutes of technology. Dublin: HEA.
- Hinostroza-Paredes, Y., (2023). Reflexivity and agency in university-based teacher educators: a critical realist analysis. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 28(8), pp.1918-1936.
- Holmes, A.G.D., (2020). Researcher Positionality--A Consideration of Its Influence and Place Qualitative Research--A New Researcher Guide. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 8(4), pp.1-10.
- Irish Universities Association, (2022). *Research Integrity*. National Forum on Research Integrity. Available at: <https://www.iaa.ie/for-researchers/research-integrity/> (Accessed 1 Nov 2024).
- Kassan, A., Nutter, S., Green, A.R., Arthur, N., Russell-Mayhew, S. and Sesma-Vasquez, M., (2020). Capturing the shadow and light of researcher positionality: a picture-prompted poly-ethnography. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19, p.1609406920977325.
- Lather, P., (2016). Top Ten+ List: (Re) Thinking Ontology in (Post) Qualitative Research. *Cultural Studies? Critical Methodologies*, 16(2), pp.125-131.
- Lincoln, Y., Guba. E., (1985). Naturalistic inquiry. *Beverly Hills: Sage. Lincoln Naturalistic Inquiry*1985.
- Luttrell, W., (2019). Reflexive qualitative research. In *Oxford research encyclopaedia of education* (pp. 1-21). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lynch, K. And O'Riordan, C. (1998) "Inequality in Higher Education: a study of class barriers", *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 19(4), pp. 445-478. Doi: 10.1080/0142569980190401.
- Maxwell, J.A., (2018). Collecting qualitative data: A realist approach. *The SAGE handbook of qualitative data collection*, pp.19-32.

McCoy, S., Byrne, D., O'Connell, P. J., Kelly, E. & Doherty, C. (2010). Hidden disadvantage? A study on the low participation in higher education by the non-manual group (Dublin, Higher Education Authority). ("Let's talk about class – exploring the everyday emotions and ...")

McLeod, J. (2015). *Doing Research in Counselling and Psychotherapy*, 3rd ed., London: Sage publications.

Mertens, D.M., (2021). Transformative research methods to increase social impact for vulnerable groups and cultural minorities. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20, p.16094069211051563.

Mertens, D.M., (2023). *Research and evaluation in education and psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods*. Sage publications.

Mullings, B., (1999). Insider or outsider, both or neither: some dilemmas of interviewing in a cross-cultural setting. *Geoforum*, 30(4), pp.337-350.

Narayanasamy, A., (2015). Reflexive account of unintended outcomes from spiritual care qualitative research. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 20(3), pp.234-248.

Njeri, S., (2021). Race, positionality and the researcher. *The companion to peace and conflict fieldwork*, pp.381-394.

O'Reilly, M. and Kiyimba, N. (2015) *Advanced Qualitative Research*. 1st edn. SAGE Publications. [Online] Available at: <https://www.perlego.com/book/1431562/advanced-qualitative-research-a-guide-to-using-theory-pdf> (Accessed: 14 October 2022).

Ortlipp, M., (2008). Keeping and using reflective journals in the qualitative research process. *The qualitative report*, 13(4), pp.695-705.

Pillow, W. (2003). Confession, catharsis, or cure? Rethinking the uses of reflexivity as methodological power in qualitative research. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 16(2), 175–196. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0951839032000060635>.

Pobal, (2022). HP Deprivation Index. [Online] Available at: <https://www.pobal.ie/research-analysis/open-data/> (Accessed 14 May 2024).

Pobal, (2023). HP Deprivation Index. [Online] Available at: <https://www.pobal.ie/research-analysis/> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

Shaw, R., (2005). Researcher Positionality and Fieldwork Practices in Organizational Research. *Organisational Research Methods*, 8(4), pp.439-457.

Smyth, E. and Banks, J., (2012). 'There Was Never Really Any Question of Anything Else': Young People's Agency, Institutional Habitus and the Transition to Higher Education. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 33(2), pp.263-281.

Torgerson, C. et al. (2014) *Higher Education access: Evidence of effectiveness of university access strategies and approaches* (London, Sutton Trust).

Unluer, S., (2012). Being an insider researcher while conducting case study research. *Qualitative Report*, 17, p.58.

Wiles, R., (2012). What are qualitative research ethics? (p. 128). Bloomsbury Academic.

Yin, R.K., (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods* (Vol. 5). SAGE.

Yin, R.K., (2015). Qualitative research from start to finish. Guilford publications.